

ANALYSIS OF MANAQIBS ABOUT UNNAMED SAINTS MENTIONED IN THE WORK “MASNAWI-YI MANAWI”

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Annotation. *This article explores the typological and historical classification of manaqibs (hagiographies) related to unnamed saints mentioned in Jalaluddin Rumi's 'Masnawi-yi Manawi'. It analyzes the narrative techniques used in the Masnawi, how individual manaqibs intertwine with one another and serve as tools of moral and spiritual instruction. The study reveals the structural coherence of Rumi's style, the symbolism behind saintly characteristics, and the Sufi understanding of divine justice, patience, and union with the divine.*

Keywords: *Masnawi-yi Manawi, Manaqib, Unnamed saints, Sufism, Jalaluddin Rumi.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada Jaloliddin Rumi tomonidan yozilgan “Masnaviyi ma’naviy” asarida tilga olingan ismsiz avliyolar haqidagi manaqiblar tipologik va tarixiy jihatdan tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada manaqiblarning ma’naviy-tarbiyaviy ahamiyati, ular orqali Rumi qanday ijtimoiy va axloqiy xulosalarni bergani, shuningdek, bu hikoyatlar orasidagi mazmuniy uyg’unlik ochib beriladi.*

Kalit soʻzlar: *Masnaviy, manaqib, ismsiz avliyolar, tasavvuf, Jaloliddin Rumi.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются типологическая и историческая классификация манакибов (жизнеописаний святых), упомянутых в «Маснави-йи ма’нави» Джалаладдина Руми. Особое внимание уделяется структуре рассказов, их взаимосвязи, а также духовно-нравственным урокам, которые Руми доносит через эти истории.*

Ключевые слова: *Маснави, манакиб, безымянные святые, суфизм, Джалаладдин Руми.*

Manaqibs, which are significant sources of Turkic literature and culture, are products of religious-mystical Turkic folk literature. Manaqibs, aimed at glorifying the life of a saint, ensuring the spread of the order to which they belong, and training disciples, are regarded as semi-sacred narratives offering insights about the social structure and other aspects of society.

Books containing the manaqibs (hagiographies) of saints, known as manaqibnomas, emerged as an independent genre from the 13th century onwards¹. The word "manqaba" originates from the Arabic root "naqaba" and means "praiseworthy deed, action, and virtue." The plural form of the word "manqaba" is manaqib².

According to the explanation in "Ghiyas ul-lughat" by Muhammad Ghiyasiddin, manaqib means "good, admirable qualities," while manqabat means "skill and praise." As a term, manqabat refers to a work dedicated to extolling the Prophet's family, caliphs, and companions³. Manaqibs, which are considered concise narratives highlighting miracles in Sufi tradition, are texts that

¹ L.L.El-Fârûkî. İslâm Kültür Atlası. – İstanbul: İnkılab Yayıncılık, 1999. – P. 325.

² A.Y.Ocak. Kültür Tarihi Kaynağı olarak menâkıbnâmeler. – Ankara, 1992. – P. 27.

³ Muhammad G‘iyosiddin. G‘iyos ul-lug‘at. Jildi 2. – Dushanbe: Adib, 1988. P. 301-303.

emerged from oral traditions transmitted orally by disciples and members of Sufi orders about the lives of saints after their deaths⁴.

Among the Turkic peoples, great figures such as Ahmad Yassavi, Mawlana Jalaluddin Rumi, Yunus Emre, Haji Bayram Vali, and Haji Bektash Vali took on the task of disseminating ideas about nurturing the perfect person through literature and art.

The poet of humanity, who had a profound influence on both Eastern and Western literature, the eminent Sufi sage and philosopher Mawlana Jalaluddin Muhammad Balkhi Rumi, known in the East as "Mawlana" and in the West as "Rumi," is recognized as one of the most influential figures in world literature. Almost every person in the Turkic world is familiar with this individual, and the entire world recognizes him as a philosopher and spiritual leader.

We deemed it necessary to study the 16 manaqibs (hagiographies) cited in Jalaluddin Rumi's "Masnawi-yi Manawi", classifying them historically and typologically into the following groups:

1. Manaqibs about saints whose names and historical identities are known.
2. Manaqibs about unnamed saints.
3. Saints whose names are only mentioned in the "Masnawi-yi Ma'navi."

In Mawlana's work "Masnawi-yi Manawi," manaqibs are presented about 8 saints whose names and historical identities are known, including Sheikh Daquqi, Ibrahim Adham, Sheikh Abdullah Maghribi, Bayazid Bistami, Sheikh Hasan Kharaqani, Sheikh Ahmad Khidravyah, Dhul-Nun al-Misri, and Sheikh Muhammad Sarrazi of Ghazni. We will discuss the content of these manaqibs in our other study.

In the "Masnawi-yi Manawi", alongside manaqibs of saints whose names and identities are known, there are also manaqibs about saints whose real names are not disclosed. The names of saints in these manaqibs are often given based on their physical characteristics.

a) Sheikh Akta

Although there is insufficient information about the life of Sheikh Akta, there is a tomb attributed to him at the foot of a mountain west of Shiraz. Sheikh Abulkhair Akta and Junayd's scribe Abu Ya'qub Akta, who are known to have died between 304 AH / 916-917 CE, are also mentioned by this name. The information about this person, described by Mawlana as one who drank the wine of Allah, loved solitude, and lived in the mountains, is limited to these details⁵.

The word "Akta" means "with cut hand." This unnamed person is called so because of the characteristic related to his hand. The content of the manaqib (hagiography) of this person, who is presented as Sheikh Akta in the work "Masnawi-yi Manawi," is as follows:

There was a dervish who lived alone in the mountains. Having drunk the wine of Allah, he had grown weary of people's chatter. In those mountains, there were trees bearing countless fruits: apples, pears, and pomegranates. The dervish sustained himself solely on these fruits. He had secluded himself in the mountains, vowing never to shake fruit from the trees, never to ask anything from anyone openly or secretly, and never to tell others to shake the trees. He pledged to eat only the fruits that fell naturally from the trees. This dervish adhered to his vow for a while but eventually faced the trials of fate. He became weak and distressed, losing the strength to move. For exactly five days, the dervish refrained from shaking the pear tree, but the fire of hunger was eroding his patience. He spotted a cluster of pears on one branch but restrained himself once

⁴ N.Küleççi. Mesnevi Edebiyatı Antolojisi. C. I. – Erzurum: Aktif Yayınevi, 1999. – P. 373.

⁵ Mevlânâ. Mesnevî. Çev: Veled Çelebi İzbudak, düzenleyen: Abdülbaki Gölpınarlı, III. – İstanbul, 1991: MEB Yayınları, P. 409.

more. Just then, the wind blew and bent the branch. The dervish immediately set aside his vow, plucked a pear from the branch, and ate it. In that instant, struck by Allah's punishment, he opened his eyes and tugged at his ears in remorse. At that time, twenty or more thieves had stopped nearby, dividing their stolen goods. One of them reported this to the Shahna (a person responsible for the region's security). The Shahna's men swiftly arrived and apprehended them all. Enraged, the Shahna ordered the executioner, "Cut off their hands and feet." The executioner began severing everyone's left legs and right hands right there. Amidst the commotion, the sheikh's hand was mistakenly cut off as well. As the executioner was about to amputate his leg, a high-ranking horseman arrived and shouted, "This is Sheikh So-and-so, Allah's chosen one. Why did you cut off his hand?" The executioner, tearing his clothes and stumbling, explained the situation to the Shahna. After assessing the circumstances, the Shahna came to apologize to the Sheikh. The Sheikh said, "I know the reason for this; I understand my sin. I abandoned the sanctity of my oath, and His justice has cut off my oath and my right hand! Knowing it was wrong, I broke my vow. The consequences of this have struck my hand. O saint, may our hands, feet, minds, and skin be sacrificed for the Beloved's judgment!" Due to this incident, the sheikh whose hand was cut off became known among the people as "Sheikh Akta - the one-handed sheikh," and people recognized him by this name⁶.

This manaqib relates that Sheikh Akta's hand was cut off for not fulfilling his promise. Through this story, Mawlana emphasizes that people should keep their word and gives the following warning: "The wise cry out in advance, while the ignorant beat their heads at the end! Ask about the outcome at the beginning of your work, so you don't regret it on the Day of Judgment"⁷.

In "Masnawi-yi Manawi", another manaqib related to Sheikh Akta mentions that this person wove a stretcher with both hands despite having a severed hand⁸.

The story of Prophet Moses is narrated in a section where this manaqib is mentioned. After this, the topic is reinforced by explaining why Pharaoh's sorcerers did not pay attention to having their hands and feet cut off⁹. In this story, because the magicians believed after seeing Moses' miracles, Pharaoh threatened to cut off their hands and feet. However, after seeing the truth, the magicians, like Sheikh Akta, accepted the decree of fate. In this way, both texts are interconnected, ensuring semantic transition and thematic integrity. Thus, Rumi "Masnawi-yi Manawi" created a very consistent and organic connection between the texts. Through this method, he established spatial connections in people's minds to convey his intended messages, made it easier to remember what was said, and kept the reader's attention constantly alert.

b) One Sheikh

It is unknown who this person is, introduced by Mawlana as a lamp belonging to heaven on earth and a sheikh who resembles a prophet among the ummah, opening the gates of the Gardens of Paradise to the people. The truth about a sheikh's crying over the death of his sons is narrated in the hagiography "Masnawi-yi Manawi" as follows:

⁶ Mevlânâ. Mesnevî. Çev: Veled Çelebi İzbudak, düzenleyen: Abdülbaki Gölpınarlı, III. – İstanbul, 1991: MEB Yayınları, P. 131-138.

⁷ Mevlânâ. Mesnevî. Çev: Veled Çelebi İzbudak, düzenleyen: Abdülbaki Gölpınarlı, III. – İstanbul, 1991: MEB Yayınları, P. 132.

⁸ Mevlânâ. Mesnevî. Çev: Veled Çelebi İzbudak, düzenleyen: Abdülbaki Gölpınarlı, III. – İstanbul, 1991: MEB Yayınları, P. 139-140.

⁹ Mevlânâ. Mesnevî. Çev: Veled Çelebi İzbudak, düzenleyen: Abdülbaki Gölpınarlı, III. – İstanbul, 1991: MEB Yayınları, P. 140-142.

The Sheikh's sons had died, but the Sheikh wasn't crying. The family asked why they had wept bitterly over the death of his sons, but why he had not wept at all. The Sheikh told his wife who had spoken these words not to think his heart was hard, as he was merciful to everyone. The woman asked, "Since you are merciful to all, how can you not cry for your own sons when death's executioner has struck them down?" Then the Sheikh replied: "The winter season is not like July. Let them all die if they will, let them live if they will. They don't disappear from the heart's eye! Why should I scratch my face like you when I see them in front of my eyes? They've left their time, but they're still with me, playing around me! Crying comes either from grief or from separation. But I am in union with my beloved ones, running with them. People see them in dreams, but I see them clearly while awake. Whether I've hidden myself from the world or shaken the leaf of feeling from the tree of existence, I am with them"¹⁰.

In Manaqib, various messages are conveyed through the manaqib of this sheikh, who is presented as a guide for people. Mawlana, whose purpose is to teach people lessons, also explains the meaning of the word "sheikh" by revealing the truth behind the sheikh's lack of crying in this manaqib:

Who is called a Sheikh? If a person is freed from only some of their human qualities, they do not become a sheikh, but rather a mature person. If not a trace of human qualities remains, they become a sheikh, a person acceptable to Allah. However, if a person simply grows old and their hair and beard turn gray, they are neither a spiritual guide nor Allah's chosen one! Even if a particle of human qualities remains in their being, they cannot belong to this category; they are merely one of the people of the world¹¹!

d) Blind Sheikh

Mawlana, without providing any information about him, introduced him as "The Blind Sheikh." The content of this person's manaqib is as follows:

A poor sheikh visited a blind pir's house in July and saw a Quran there. He wondered to himself, "What use is a Quran here, when this person is blind?" However, he remained patient and decided not to ask anything. He waited patiently, feeling uneasy for a while, but finally understood the matter. For patience is the key to understanding. Suddenly, the mystery was solved, and he realized what he had been trying to comprehend. At midnight, he heard the sound of the Holy Quran. He jumped up from his sleep and witnessed this miraculous event. The blind man was reading the Holy Quran from the manuscript, and he was reading it correctly. Unable to contain himself, he asked the sheikh about the reason for this phenomenon. The blind man replied, "O you who have been freed from bodily ignorance, can Allah not do this? Why are you surprised? I prayed to Allah: 'O Allah, my helper, O Allah, from whom help is sought, as much as people love their lives, I am devoted to reading the Holy Quran. But I am not a hafiz! Oh Lord, when I read the Holy Quran, grant my eyes flawless sight. Open my eyes so that I may take the Holy Quran and recite it.' And Allah accepted my prayer. Whenever I wish to read the Holy Quran, whenever I pick up the manuscript, Allah bestows light upon my eyes like a night lamp"¹².

¹⁰ Mevlânâ. *Mesnevî*. Çev: Veled Çelebi İzbudak, düzenleyen: Abdülbaki Gölpınarlı, III. – İstanbul, 1991: MEB Yayınları, S. 144-149.

¹¹ Mevlânâ. *Mesnevî*. Çev: Veled Çelebi İzbudak, düzenleyen: Abdülbaki Gölpınarlı, III. – İstanbul, 1991: MEB Yayınları, S. 145-146.

¹² Mevlânâ. *Mesnevî*. Çev: Veled Çelebi İzbudak, düzenleyen: Abdülbaki Gölpınarlı, III. – İstanbul, 1991: MEB Yayınları, P. 149-152.

Mawlana, drawing from the exemplary life of this person who, not dissatisfied with his blindness, looked at life with hope, emphasizes the importance of people seeing not their own shortcomings and negative aspects, but rather the positive aspects in any situation:

Whatever Allah takes, He gives something in return. For this reason, the saint does not object to Allah. Did He take your garden? He will grant you a garden full of grapes. If you are in sorrow, He brings joy. He gives hands to those without arms and legs, and brings joy and elation to the hearts of those drowning in sorrow. If what we have lost is very significant and valuable, yet we are receiving a gift in return, then we have no reason to object¹³.

Mawlana, in the exemplary story, reinforces the fact that the ascetic, despite witnessing the blind sheikh reading the Quran, patiently refrained from asking questions, comparing it to how Luqman, upon seeing Hazrat Dovud making iron rings, restrained his curiosity and did not ask questions.

Mawlana, whose name can be preceded by many honorific titles, is also a "famous teacher"¹⁴. While presenting solutions to negative situations in society, through this exemplary story, he emphasizes the importance of patience and describes it as the "key to contentment and happiness" as follows:

"He was patient, though for a while he felt distressed, but finally he understood the essence of the matter. Because patience is the key to broadness"¹⁵.

If a person waits patiently without rushing in any situation, the true essence of the matter becomes clear: "Patience is also a beautiful thing. One should rely on it in any pain, it will remove any sorrow. Allah created thousands of chemicals, but man has not seen such a miraculous chemistry as patience"¹⁶.

In the work "Masnawi-yi Manawi," along with the description of the aforementioned saints and their manaqıbs, only the names of some saints are mentioned or their famous sayings are emphasized. One of such saints is Mansur Hallaj. His real name was Husayn ibn Mansur al-Hallaj, and he was born in 857 AH / 244 AD in the village of Tur near the city of Bayza in Iran. Having chosen the path of Sufism from a young age, Mansur Hallaj traveled to India and Turkic states, trying to spread Islam in these places. He conversed with great figures like Abdullah Tustari and Junayd Baghdadi, reached the state of fanafillah in Sufism, and proclaimed "Anal Haq." Mansur Hallaj, who was executed for this proclamation, was recognized as a martyr of love, and many Sufis quoted his words in their works¹⁷.

Although "Masnawi-yi Manawi" does not include any story about Mansur Hallaj, his phrase "Anal Haq" is interpreted as follows: A person without sorrow is a highwayman, and sorrowlessness means "Anal Haq - I am the Truth." Saying this "Ana" (I am) at the right time is a

¹³ Mevlânâ. *Mesnevî*. Çev: Veled Çelebi İzbudak, düzenleyen: Abdülbaki Gölpınarlı, III. – İstanbul, 1991: MEB Yayınları, P. 152.

¹⁴ Akyüz Yahya. *Türk Eğitim Tarihi*. – Ankara: Pegem A Yayıncılık, 2008, P. 54.

¹⁵ Mevlânâ. *Mesnevî*. Çev: Veled Çelebi İzbudak, düzenleyen: Abdülbaki Gölpınarlı, III. – İstanbul, 1991: MEB Yayınları, P. 150.

¹⁶ Mevlânâ. *Mesnevî*. Çev: Veled Çelebi İzbudak, düzenleyen: Abdülbaki Gölpınarlı, III. – İstanbul, 1991: MEB Yayınları, P. 151.

¹⁷ Mevlânâ. *Mesnevî*. Çev: Veled Çelebi İzbudak, düzenleyen: Abdülbaki Gölpınarlı, II. – İstanbul, 1991: MEB Yayınları, P. 200.

blessing, but saying it inappropriately is a curse. Mansur's saying "Ana" undoubtedly consists only of mercy. But look at Pharaoh saying "Ana" - it is the curse itself¹⁸.

"Masnawi-yi Manawi" also mentions another saint - Junayd Baghdadi. Although this person, who was one of the great saints, is known by the name Junayd Baghdadi, his real name is Junayd ibn Muhammad Abulqasim al-Jazza. He was born in 207 AH (822 AD) in the city of Nahavand, Iran and died in 298 AH (911 AD) in Baghdad. Due to his high status in science and religion, he was known by the title "Tawus ul-Ulama" (Peacock of the Scholars) in his time¹⁹.

Junayd Baghdadi, like Mansur Hallaj, is very famous for his shathiyat (ecstatic utterances). In the Masnawi, Mawlana describes Junayd Baghdadi as the "pole of the mystics" and writes about him:

*"When Junayd received help from His (Allah's) soldiers, his achievements became countless. When Bayazid found the way to His favor, he heard the name "Qutb ul-arifin" (the pole of the gnostics) from Allah. And Edhem's son, having joyfully ridden his horse in that direction, became the sultan of just sultans"*²⁰.

In "Masnawi Manawi," there are saints whose names are only mentioned without any description of their manaqibs (hagiographies), and they are as follows:

1. Shaybani Roi²¹.
2. Sheikh ul-Islam Taj Balkh and his brother Ziyoi Dalk²².

The adoption of Islam by Turkic peoples and the widespread dissemination of tariqats in Anatolia led to the rapid spread of manaqibs formed around the lives of saints in a very short time. These individuals, who guided the minds and hearts of disciples through words in the process of Sufi education, extensively used manaqibs of literary and aesthetic significance in their conversations. Thus, they aimed to teach people various lessons through the exemplary actions of saints.

Mawlana, who set himself the goal of reaching people of all classes and enlightening them, also used manaqibs in the "Masnawi" as an appropriate form for conveying his thoughts. Putting his ideas into this form, he explained each manaqib with other examples related to the topic, reinforcing his concepts.

The distribution of manaqibs found in the "Masnawi" is as follows:

1. Sheikh Daquqiy - 1.
2. Ibrahim Adham - 2.
3. Sheikh Abdullah Maghribi - 1.
4. Bayazid Bistami - 3,
5. Sheikh Hasan Haraqani - 2.
6. Sheikh Ahmad Khidravayh - 1.
7. Zunnun al-Misri - 1.

¹⁸ Mevlânâ. *Mesnevî*. Çev: Veled Çelebi İzbudak, düzenleyen: Abdülbaki Gölpınarlı, II. – İstanbul, 1991: MEB Yayınları, P. 200.

¹⁹ Aktaş Hasan. *Yeni Türk Şiirinde İbrahim Edhem Okulu ve Misyonu*. – Edirne: Yort Savul Yayınları, 2008, P. 23-24.

²⁰ Mevlânâ. *Mesnevî*. Çev: Veled Çelebi İzbudak, düzenleyen: Abdülbaki Gölpınarlı, II. – İstanbul, 1991: MEB Yayınları, P. 71.

²¹ Mevlânâ. *Mesnevî*. Çev: Veled Çelebi İzbudak, düzenleyen: Abdülbaki Gölpınarlı, VI. – İstanbul, 1991: MEB Yayınları, P. 383.

²² Mevlânâ. *Mesnevî*. Çev: Veled Çelebi İzbudak, düzenleyen: Abdülbaki Gölpınarlı, VI. – İstanbul, 1991: MEB Yayınları, P. 283.

8. Ghaznavid Sheikh Muhammad Sarrazi - 1.

Additionally, there are also some manaqibs about saints whose identities are not explicitly indicated:

1. Sheikh Akta - 2,
2. A certain Sheikh - 1.
3. Blind Sheikh - 1.

Additionally, although the names of saints such as Hallaj Mansur, Junayd Baghdadi, Shaybani Ra'i, Sheikh ul-Islam Taj Balkh and his brother Ziyai Dalk are mentioned, no hagiographies related to them are presented.

These hagiographies are not presented as a cohesive whole, but rather interwoven with other texts. Although they may initially appear to be presented in a fragmented style, this approach is an expression of Mawlana's creative imagination. When Mawlana narrates one event, he alludes to others, thus interweaving verses, hadiths, wise sayings, stories, hagiographies, and manaqibs in a rich, interconnected style.

Consequently, the texts in "Masnawi" are intricately connected, and it becomes evident that the stories within it are not disjointed, but possess a strong logical structure. Through this method, Mawlana ensured that the ideas conveyed were more deeply embedded in the human consciousness, making them easier to memorize, while also managing to keep the reader's attention constantly engaged.

Mawlana provided a general conclusion at the end of each hagiography, offering brief insights that serve as lessons for the reader. In this way, the hagiographies address issues pertaining to both individuals and society, presenting topics in a highly fluent and impactful style supported by reliable evidence.

These characteristics demonstrate Mawlana's skill in conveying his thoughts in the most precise and comprehensible manner, using hagiographies as a medium.

In conclusion, "Masnawi" is a perfect masterpiece that retains its relevance in any era as one of the most important works of Turkic culture and literature. It has been determined that if all the manaqibs (hagiography) in it were compiled, they could form an independent manaqibnoma (a work dedicated to the lives of saints).

Generally speaking, Jalaluddin Rumi's manaqibs embody various principles of moral education and recommendations given to scholars, and the poet's teachings serve to nurture a spiritually elevated, perfect individual. Moreover, in all the scholar's works, people are encouraged to live in harmony with society and nature, to avoid harming living beings for personal gain, and to set an example as a perfect person. Jalaliddin Rumi's spiritual and moral views and teachings on cultivating a perfect individual are significant not only for people of his time but also for those of today. Rumi's work can be likened to a vast and fathomless ocean. Everyone drinks from it as much as their vessel can hold. The deeper you dive into this ocean; the more priceless treasures you discover.

REFERENCES

1. Chittick, W. C. (1983). *The Sufi Path of Love: The Spiritual Teachings of Rumi*. SUNY Press.
2. Ernst, C. W. (1997). *The Shambhala Guide to Sufism*. Shambhala Publications.
3. Karamustafa, A. T. (2007). *Sufism: The Formative Period*. University of California Press.
4. Rumi, J. (2004). *The Masnawi: Book One*. Translated by Jawid Mojaddedi. Oxford University Press.

5. Ruzmanova, R. (2021). Alisher Navoiy g'azalları ta'sırıda yozilgan 33 nazira. *Alisher Navoiy Xalqaro jurnal*, (1), 205-210.
6. Ruzmanova, R.U. (2015). Ali Şir Nevâî Şiirlerinde Sanat Tekniklerinin kullanılması. *Kardeş Kalemler*, 9(103), 47-51.
7. Ruzmanova, R.U. (2020). Naziranavislik an'analari haqıda. *So'z san'ati xalqaro jurnali*, 3-jild, 2-son, 158-165.
8. Schimmel, A. (1975). *Mystical Dimensions of Islam*. University of North Carolina Press.
9. Sultanov Tulkin Irgashevich. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE FIRST TURKIC TAZKIRAS. *Alisher Navoi*. 2022, vol. 2, issue 2, (147-159) pp.
10. Sultanov, T. (2023). ALİ ŞİR NEVÂYÎ'NİN ESERLERİNİN AZERBAIJAN EDEBİYATINA ETKİSİ. *Uluslararası Türk Lehçe Araştırmaları Dergisi (TÜRKLAD)*, 7(2), 335-346. <https://doi.org/10.30563/turklad.1279465>
11. Sultanov, T., Ablakulova, I., Halimova, N., Husanova D., Ananth C. and Kumar, T.A. (2024). "Textual Analysis and Computational Insights into Alisher Navoi's 'Divan of the AqQoyunlu Admirers'," *2024 Ninth International Conference on Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (ICONSTEM)*, Chennai, India, pp. 1-7, doi: 10.1109/ICONSTEM60960.2024.10568828.
12. Sultanov, T.I. (2018). Ali Şir Nevâî Şiirinin Sadık Bey Sadıkî Sanatına Etkisi. *Dil ve edebiyat araştırmaları Uluslararası dergisi*, 18, 277-285.